

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN : 2349-7750

INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES

SJIF Impact Factor: 7.187

Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

RISE IN THE OCCURRENCE OF TYPE 2 DIABETES MELLITUS INDEPENDENTLY OF ALCOHOL CONSUMPTION, BMI AND TRIGLYCERIDES

¹Dr Manzoor Hussain, ²Muhammad Shawaiz Tariq, ³Waqar Arshad¹Registrar, Medical A unit, MTI/Mardan Medical Complex, Mardan²Medical Officer, Dhigurah Health Centre Maldives³Senior House Officer Emergency Medicine South Tipperary General Hospital, Clonmel, Ireland

Article Received: October 2020

Accepted: November 2020

Published: December 2020

Abstract:

Aim: To tentatively explore whether synchronous rise of gamma-glutamyl transferase and alanine aminotransferase is related with the expansion of type 2 diabetes mellitus rate free of liquor drinking, body mass file and fatty oils.

Methods: A total of 2,778 Japanese workers who had no experience with type 2 diabetes mellitus were followed up. High levels of GGT and ALT were characterized as the upper tertiles (GGT cut-off point: 49 IU/L, ALT cut-off point: 28 IU/L). Our current research was conducted at Services Hospital, Lahore from May 2019 to April 2020. Three replications were performed using these dichotomized GGT and ALT cut-off points: both low, either high, or both high. The multivariate Cox relative risk models were modified to account for variables that could be perplexing.

Results: A total of 279 cases of type 2 diabetes mellitus were recognized during 12 years (28,070 men over extended periods) of follow-up. Members whose GGT and ALT were elevated during this time had a significantly higher rate of type 2 diabetes mellitus, even after the change to fasting insulin and contrasting fasting blood glucose and no height GGT or ALT collection. Comparative affiliations were observed in both non-alcohol and lightly alcoholic drinkers, as well as in members with a typical weight. However, the affiliation was more fragile in members with fatty oils <156 mg/dL. We then evaluated whether the expansion of GGT and ALT would improve the prediction of type 2 diabetes mellitus, and found that their incorporation fundamentally expanded measure C, with the net improvement in naming also incorporating the improvement in segregation.

Conclusion: Simultaneous rise of GGT and ALT was essentially connected with type 2 diabetes mellitus rate, free of expected frustrating components, including liquor drinking and weight, despite the fact that the affiliation may require corresponding height of fatty substances. Incorporation of GGT and ALT improved sort 2 diabetes mellitus hazard forecast.

Keywords: Alcohol Consumption, BMI, Triglycerides, Type-2 Diabetes.

Corresponding author:**Dr Manzoor Hussain,**

Registrar, Medical A unit, MTI/Mardan Medical Complex, Mardan

QR code

Please cite this article in press Manzoor Hussain et al, *Rise In The Occurrence Of Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus Independently Of Alcohol Consumption, Bmi And Triglycerides.*, Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2020; 07(12).

INTRODUCTION:

The diabetes mellitus pandemic is a global public welfare issue. In Japan, the prevalence of diabetes mellitus is expected to increase from 8.6% to 8.9% over the next two decades. Understanding the pathophysiological pathways that lead to type 2 diabetes mellitus would be important to develop powerful and effective anticipatory programs [1]. The liver plays an important role in directing blood glucose levels, particularly during fasting, and liver damage demonstrated by elevated blood alanine aminotransferase or gamma-glutamyl transferase levels has been reported to raise the incidence of type 2 diabetes mellitus [2]. These proteins are thought to be markers of basic liver pathology, such as fat collection in the liver or extreme alcohol absorption, while an ongoing Mendelian randomization study recommends that ALT may be a causative factor [3]. Hence, we have chosen to study the relationship between ALT and GGT and the improvement of type 2 diabetes mellitus in a partner of middle-aged Japanese men, not only by factually controlling for probably confounding factors, but also by conducting a few investigations separated by significant confounding or intermediate factors, counting alcohol intake, body fat and hypertriglyceridemia. In addition, it would be clinically relevant to analyze the simultaneous elevation of ALT and GGT levels, and its relationship with improvement in type 2 diabetes mellitus [4]. While past cross-sectional examinations have shown that the mixture of higher GGT and ALT had a positive relationship with type 2 diabetes mellitus, there is limited imminent examination of this question. Since a huge and measurable affiliation does not really demonstrate the value of waiting, we too have evaluated the progressive presumptive estimation of liver compounds [5].

METHODOLOGY:

In 2009, 6,676 Japanese public servants aged 36 to 68 became interested in the Wave 2 benchmarking study by responding to self-administered surveys and

providing data from their mandatory annual welfare test. The current review was initially limited to 6,179 male members, given the modest number of cases of type 2 diabetes mellitus in women observed in the following period. Our current research was conducted at Services Hospital, Lahore from May 2019 to April 2020. Accompanying members were then successively avoided : (i) 842 individuals did not consent to the use of clinical history or wellness test data; (ii) 448 common cases of type 2 diabetes mellitus at baseline, characterized by self-reported drug use or a reference fasting blood glucose (FBG) level ≥ 129 mg/dL or glycated hemoglobin $\geq 7.8\%$ (according to the strategy of the U.S. National Glycohemoglobin Standardization Program) ; (iii) 1,108 individuals who do not qualify for standard fasting insulin, FBG or smoking status; and (iv) four individuals who have reached adulthood ≥ 67 years of age at the reference point. Thus, 2,779 members were left for analysis. Membership ended December 31, 2014. Individual years were determined from the model up to the date of publication, recognition of the onset of type 2 diabetes mellitus, or the end of development, whichever occurred first. Members were marked with blue pencil when they kicked the bucket or resigned from their position, with the exception of those who consented to give their data on the history of their well-being to scientists after retirement (47.9% of retirees). Cases of type 2 diabetes mellitus were determined through annual wellness reviews required in the workplace until retirement and surveys during work activities, as well as after retirement. In the previous case, the information from the wellness reviews was inspected annually, and the frequency of type 2 diabetes mellitus was characterized as occurring when the BFG level initially became ≥ 129 mg/dL or the glycated hemoglobin became $\geq 7.8\%$. The glycated hemoglobin test was administered separately to representatives who were 40, 45, 50 and 56 years of age until 2007, and to those with positive urine glucose after 2009.

Table 1:

	Gamma-glutamyl transferase (GGT)		Alanine aminotransferase (ALT)		Combination of gamma-glutamyl transferase and alanine aminotransferase		
	Low (T1 < 70 U/L)	High (T2 > 70 U/L)	Low (T1 < 25 U/L)	High (T2 > 25 U/L)	Both low	Either high	Both high
All subjects	n = 2422	n = 982	n = 1885	n = 982	n = 1425	n = 982	n = 982
No diabetes	176	76	176	76	46	46	46
Diabetes	2026	906	1709	906	1379	936	936
GGT (median)	71	362	77	73	63	111	142
ALT (median)	88	112 (IQR 48-188)	89	100 (IQR 51-167)	89	140 (IQR 70-210)	140 (IQR 70-210)
Smoking status							
GGT (median)	n = 1444	n = 476	n = 1280	n = 488	n = 1165	n = 476	n = 476
No smokers	58	31	44	44	44	44	44
Smokers	1486	445	1236	444	1121	432	432
GGT (median)	71	49	64	73	61	111	142
ALT (median)	89	101 (IQR 52-170)	83	117 (IQR 60-188)	83	140 (IQR 70-210)	140 (IQR 70-210)
GGT (median)	n = 982	n = 488	n = 340	n = 378	n = 288	n = 288	n = 288
No smokers	22	7	11	11	11	11	11
Smokers	960	481	329	367	277	277	277
GGT (median)	62	70	74	72	64	111	142
ALT (median)	85	113 (IQR 54-194)	76	100 (IQR 51-167)	87	140 (IQR 70-210)	140 (IQR 70-210)
Body mass index							
GGT (median)	n = 1885	n = 982	n = 1285	n = 488	n = 1165	n = 288	n = 288
No smokers	73	42	66	47	47	47	47
Smokers	1812	940	1219	441	1118	241	241
GGT (median)	62	70	65	73	63	111	142
ALT (median)	89	113 (IQR 54-194)	81	100 (IQR 51-167)	87	140 (IQR 70-210)	140 (IQR 70-210)
GGT (median)	n = 155	n = 62	n = 39	n = 52	n = 39	n = 39	n = 39
No smokers	17	8	4	4	4	4	4
Smokers	138	54	35	48	35	35	35
GGT (median)	78	99	108	102	74	111	142
ALT (median)	97	113 (IQR 54-194)	97	100 (IQR 51-167)	97	140 (IQR 70-210)	140 (IQR 70-210)
Hypertension							
GGT (median)	n = 1385	n = 618	n = 1045	n = 398	n = 1185	n = 398	n = 398
No diabetes	36	17	31	31	31	31	31
Diabetes	1349	601	1014	367	1154	367	367
GGT (median)	63	74 (IQR 38-130)	67	74 (IQR 38-130)	67	111	142
ALT (median)	83	118 (IQR 57-200)	83	100 (IQR 51-167)	83	140 (IQR 70-210)	140 (IQR 70-210)
Cholesterol							
GGT (median)	n = 1885	n = 982	n = 1285	n = 488	n = 1165	n = 288	n = 288
No smokers	46	25	47	47	47	47	47
Smokers	1839	957	1238	441	1118	241	241
GGT (median)	67	73	74	76	68	111	142
ALT (median)	83	113 (IQR 54-194)	87	100 (IQR 51-167)	87	140 (IQR 70-210)	140 (IQR 70-210)

RESULTS:

The average age of the members of the current survey was 49.5 years. Members of the most notable GGT classification were also more established, necessarily current smokers (Table 1). As well, their blood alcohol level, BMI, fat, fasting insulin, and GFG blood levels were significantly higher. Members of the larger ALT class were also more established and had higher BMI and blood levels of fat, fasting insulin and GFG. Alcohol consumption and smoking status did not contrast between the ALT tertile classifications. Over the next 13 years, 279 of 2,778 Japanese workers (28,046 man-years) developed type 2 diabetes mellitus. The overall unrefined incidence rate was 13.3

per 1,000 man-years. It was reported that the vast majority of potentially confounding factors were related to the rate of type 2 diabetes mellitus, apart from standard actual movement and aggregate cholesterol (Table 2). Frequency rates have risen, as indicated by the expansion of the GGT or ALT classifications (Table 3). The variable HRs of type 2 diabetes mellitus in males in the most notable GGT or ALT classifications were contrasted, and the lowest tertile was basically higher than solidarity. Other changes in fasting insulin, FBG, and all liver compounds reduced the huge affiliation of GGT to type 2 diabetes mellitus, but not that of ALT.

Table 2:

Prediction model	C-statistic (95% CI)	IDI (95% CI)	P-value	NRI (95% CI)	P-value
Base model	0.747 (0.717–0.778)	REF	<0.05	REF	<0.05
Base model + Ln-GGT	0.754 (0.724–0.784)	0.007 (0.001–0.018)	<0.05	0.130 (0.055–0.198)	<0.01
Base model	0.747 (0.715–0.779)	REF	<0.05	REF	<0.01
Base model + Ln-ALT	0.754 (0.723–0.785)	0.010 (0.002–0.022)	<0.01	0.130 (0.051–0.212)	<0.01
Base model	0.747 (0.714–0.780)	REF	<0.01	REF	<0.01
Base model + Ln-GGT +Ln- ALT + Int	0.755 (0.723–0.788)	0.012 (0.006–0.026)	<0.05	0.134 (0.056–0.207)	0.060
Base model + Ln-GGT	0.754 (0.723–0.785)	REF	<0.05	REF	0.106
Base model + Ln-GGT + Ln- ALT + Int	0.755 (0.725–0.786)	0.004 (0.000–0.015)	0.159	0.135 (–0.004–0.186)	
Base model + Ln-ALT	0.754 (0.724–0.785)	REF		REF	
Base model + Ln-ALT + Ln- GGT + Int	0.755 (0.725–0.785)	0.002 (0.000–0.010)		0.096 (–0.039–0.156)	

Total sample n = 2,775. Base model included age, family history of diabetes (yes/no), regular physical activity (yes/no), current, smoking status (yes/no), alcohol consumption (g/day), body mass index (kg/m²), triglycerides, high-density lipoprotein cholesterol, total cholesterol, fasting insulin, fasting blood glucose as categories (<100, 100–109 and ≥110). ALT, alanine aminotransferase, CI, confidence interval; GGT, gamma-glutamyl transferase; Int, interaction for logarithmically transformed gamma-glutamyl transferase × logarithmically transformed alanine aminotransferase; IDI, integrated discrimination improvement; Ln, logarithmically transformed; NRI, net reclassification improvement; REF, reference; T, tertile.

Table 3:

		Crude HR (95% CI)
Age (years)	Per 1 year	1.0 (1.0–1.1)
Family history of diabetes (yes)		1.9 (1.4–2.5)
Regular physical activity (yes)		0.8 (0.6–1.1)
Current smoking status (yes)		1.5 (1.2–2.0)
Alcohol intake (g/day)	Per 1 g/day	1.0 (1.0–1.0)
Ln-body mass index (kg/m ²)	Per 1 SD	1.4 (1.3–1.6)
Ln-triglycerides (mg/dL)	Per 1 SD	1.4 (1.3–1.6)
Ln-HDL-c (mg/dL)	Per 1 SD	0.7 (0.7–0.8)
Ln-total cholesterol (mg/dL)	Per 1 SD	1.1 (0.9–1.2)
Fasting blood glucose		
<100 mg/dL		REF
100–109 mg/dL		3.2 (2.4–4.2)
≥110 mg/dL		6.8 (5.0–9.3)
Ln-fasting insulin (μU/mL)	Per 1 SD	1.4 (1.3–1.6)

Total sample $n = 2,775$. Standard deviation (SD) for logarithmically transformed (Ln)(body mass index) = 0.1; SD for Ln(triglycerides) = 0.6; SD for Ln(high-density lipoprotein cholesterol) = 0.3; SD for Ln(total cholesterol) = 0.2; SD for Ln(fasting insulin) = 0.7. HDL-c, high-density lipoprotein cholesterol; REF indicates reference.

DISCUSSION:

The current investigation showed that the synchronous rise in GGT and ALT was entirely related to improvement in type 2 diabetes mellitus, even after changes in fasting insulin and FBG levels. Furthermore, this affiliation was found in uninformed or unsophisticated consumers or in members with typical body weights, ruling out any possibility of questioning these factors [6]. Curiously, the huge affiliation was found in members with high levels of fatty oil, but not in members with typical fat levels. The present impending survey is a continuation and extension of the results of past cross-sectional studies [7]. The change for additional factors, such as fasting insulin and fasting blood glucose, has been made. In addition, defined tests were carried out by alcohol consumption status, overweight and hypertriglyceridemia in the current survey [8]. Significant affiliations observed in unsuspecting or unsophisticated drinkers, as well as in people with a typical weight, showed that ALT and GGT size would raise the risk of type 2 diabetes mellitus, independent of alcohol consumption and overweight [9-10].

CONCLUSION:

All in all, a concomitant rise in ALT and GGT has been associated with a higher rate of type 2 diabetes mellitus over a 13-year period in middle-aged Japanese men who were independent of alcohol

consumption and weight. This positive affiliation was not observed in men with typical fatty oil levels.

REFERENCES:

1. NCD Risk Factor Collaboration. Worldwide trends in diabetes since 1980: a pooled analysis of 751 population-based studies with 4.4 million participants. *Lancet* 2016; **387**: 1513– 1530.
2. Charvat H, Goto A, Goto M, *et al*. Impact of population aging on trends in diabetes prevalence: a meta-regression analysis of 160,000 Japanese adults. *J Diabetes Investig* 2015; **6**: 533– 542.
3. Rui L. Energy metabolism in the liver. *Compr Physiol* 2014; **4**: 177– 197.
4. Kunutsor SK, Apekey TA, Walley J. Liver aminotransferases and risk of incident type 2 Diabetes: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Am J Epidemiol* 2013; **178**: 159– 171.
5. Fraser A, Harris R, Sattar N, *et al*. Alanine aminotransferase, gamma-glutamyltransferase, and incident diabetes: the British Women's Heart and Health Study and meta-analysis. *Diabetes Care* 2009; **32**: 741– 750.
6. Kunutsor SK, Abbasi A, Adler AI. Gamma-glutamyl transferase and risk of type II diabetes: an updated systematic review and dose-response meta-analysis. *Ann Epidemiol* 2014; **24**: 809– 816.

7. Abbasi A, Sahlqvist AS, Lotta L, *et al.* A systematic review of biomarkers and risk of incident type 2 diabetes: an overview of epidemiological, prediction and aetiological research literature. *PLoS ONE* 2016; **11**: e0163721.
8. Nano J, Muka T, Ligthart S, *et al.* Gamma-glutamyltransferase levels, prediabetes and type 2 diabetes: a mendelian randomization study. *Int J Epidemiol* 2017; **46**: 1400– 1409.
9. Noordam R, Smit RA, Postmus I, *et al.* Assessment of causality between serum gamma-glutamyltransferase and type 2 diabetes mellitus using publicly available data: a Mendelian randomization study. *Int J Epidemiol* 2016; **45**: 1953– 1960.
10. Liu JX, Yeung SLA, Lin SL, *et al.* Liver enzymes and risk of ischemic heart disease and type 2 diabetes mellitus: a Mendelian randomization study. *Sci Rep* 2016; **6**: 38813.